

Ufra-infected plants in Orissa, India, 1987.

in size, often partially emerged, deformed, and chaffy (see figure).

Large numbers of males and juveniles but only a few females of the nematode were recovered from the axils of affected boot leaves.

Symptoms of ufra had been found before in Cuttack and Balasore, but the nematode could not be recovered. The current identification confirms presence of the nematode in a new locality and in a new habitat. □

Population dynamics of rice root nematode *Hirschmanniella oryzae* in rice of different durations

L. Arayungsarit and S. Junbuthong, Pathum Thani Rice Research Center, Thanyaburi Pathum Thani 12110, Thailand

We measured the population density of *H. oryzae* from 500-cm³ soil samples taken monthly in Jul-Dec 1987 from field plots where RD25, RD27, and LPT123 were grown as short-, medium-, and long-duration varieties. RD27 and LPT123 were seeded in Jul, RD25 in Aug. RD25 was harvested in Nov, RD27 in Dec, and LPT123 in Jan.

Nematodes (no./500 cm³ soil)

Density of rice root nematode *H. oryzae* in rice varieties of different durations at Pathum Thani Rice Research Center, Thailand, 1987 wet season.

Nematode population in RD25 had only one peak—in Nov (see figure). Both RD27 and LPT123 had two

peaks—Aug and Nov. Highest population density in all varieties occurred in Nov. □

Host range and feeding preference of golden apple snail

R. P. Basilio and J. A. Litsinger, Entomology Department, IRRI

Golden apple snail *Pomacea canaliculata* has become an important

pest of rice in the Philippines. During the pre-planting period, golden apple snails are usually found in irrigation canals and drainage ditches, where they may be feeding on weeds.

We tested eight common species of lowland weeds and rice to determine the host range and feeding preference of golden apple snail.

Table 1. Golden apple snail host preference. IRRI, 1987.

Plant species	Plants (5%) consumed by the snails ^a at indicated time (h after infestation)			
	4 h	24 h	48 h	72 h
<i>Monochoria vaginalis</i>	50 a	100 a	100 a	100 a
<i>Echinochloa glabrescens</i>	40 a	100 a	100 a	100 a
<i>Cyperus difformis</i>	35 a	90 a	100 a	100 a
<i>Oryza sativa</i>	0 b	100 a	100 a	100 a
<i>Fimbristylis miliacea</i>	0 b	100 a	100 a	100 a
<i>Paspalum distichum</i>	20 ab	55 b	85 ab	90 a
<i>Ipomoea aquatica</i>	0 b	20 c	75 b	85 a
<i>Sphenoclea zeylanica</i>	0 b	48 b	52 c	52 b
<i>Pistia stratiotes</i>	0 b	30 bc	45 c	48 b

^aAv of 10 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

Table 2. Young and old plants as preferred hosts of golden apple snail. IRRI, 1987.

Plant species	Plants consumed (%) 48 h after infestation ^a	
	Young	Old
<i>Monochoria vaginalis</i>	93 a	54 b
<i>Paspalum distichum</i>	18 a	15 b
<i>Echinochloa glabrescens</i>	77 a	6 b
<i>Cyperus difformis</i>	68 a	58 b
<i>Fimbristylis miliacea</i>	59 a	27 b
<i>Sphenoclea zeylanica</i>	50 a	32 b
<i>Pistia stratiotes</i>	28 a	24 b
<i>Ipomoea aquatica</i>	6 a	1 b

^aAv of 5 replications. In a row, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

Each female (4-5 cm height) was given 0.5 g of each test weed species (20- to 30-d-old) on 29-cm-diam GI sheet trays covered with mylar film cages. The setup had 10 replications. The amount consumed by the snails is shown in Table 1.

In a separate experiment, 7 g each of 2 weed stages (20- to 30-d-old and more than 40-d-old) were placed on each GI sheet tray and infested with 2 golden apple snails/ tray. The experiment had 5 replications. The amounts consumed by the snails were compared (Table 2).

Golden apple snails appear to have a wide host range and to feed on almost all lowland weeds. They prefer the soft, young parts of the plant. □

Single-dose anticoagulants for rodent control in irrigated ricefields

G. Chopra, Zoology Department, Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra 132119, India

We tested two singledose anticoagulants—bromadiolone and brodifacoum—to establish the appropriate time for rodent poison baiting.

Of 15 rodent species of economic importance in India, *Bandicota bengalensis*, *Rattus melstada*, and field mice *Mus* spp. cause huge rice crop losses in northern India. At early stages

Rodent activity (%)

1. Exposure of 0.005% bromadiolone bai at different weeks after transplanting. Arrows indicate time of poison baiting. Treatment at a) 4 WT, b) 6 WT, c) 8 WT, d) 10 WT, e) 12 WT, f) multiple baiting, g) continuous baiting in bamboo bait stations, h) activity in reference fields.

of rice growth, the rodents are confined to bunds and adjacent permanent pathways. They migrate inside the fields at crop maturity. As much as 12% tiller

damage by rodents was assessed in reference fields.

Treatment for rodents on bunds and adjacent pathways at 8-10 wk after